

THE BASIC FEATURES OF LANGUAGE COMPETENCE IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *The purpose of this article is to inform readers about the main features of language competence in foreign language teaching. The article also provides information on the effectiveness of the learner-centered approach in the development of language competencies.*

Keywords: *language competence, learner-centered approach, phonetic competence, grammatical competence, lexical competence.*

ОСНОВНЫЕ ПРИЗНАКИ ЯЗЫКОВОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. *Цель данной статьи является информирование читателей об основных особенностях языковых компетенций при обучении иностранному языку. В статье также представлена информация об эффективности лично-ориентированного подхода в развитии языковых компетенций.*

Ключевые слова: *языковые компетенции, лично-ориентированный подход, фонетическая компетенция, грамматическая компетенция, лексическая компетенция.*

One of the main tasks of the learner centered approach is to increase the student's autonomy, and these skills are a combination of acquired life skills that help the student in the learning process, in other words. Learning and practice outside the classroom are just as important for successful language acquisition as in the classroom. And for this, students will need additional guidance and support. Learner centered approach to the development of language competence in the process of learning a foreign language can also help to achieve an effective result.

Based on the definitions and analysis presented to the learner centered approach, it can be said that it is advisable to create an interactive language learning environment, adapting learner centered approach education to the wishes and capabilities of the student and integrating it with the type of education and form of training that is considered effective in language learning. It should be noted that in the theory of teaching foreign languages, two terms are equally common, namely linguistic competence and language competence. <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Linguistic> according to the competence page, linguistic competence or language competence is a system of linguistic knowledge acquired by users of a language as a native language. Language competence differs from language use during communication (language performance). The concept of communicative competence of a foreign language is manifested in the works of several researchers and differs from each other in that it is illuminated through different approaches.

Despite the fact that the concept of communicative competence of a foreign language is interpreted differently, communicative competence of a foreign language for teachers of a foreign language is one of the main features of their professional activity. By analyzing the definitions that experts have given rise to communicative competence, combining various components and expressing the professional growth of activity in foreign languages, we understand that the specialist's ability and willingness, the choice of communicative behavior

using the norms of the foreign language system correctly, is able to communicate effectively in real life and can teach this to his students and develop their communicative abilities in the future.

The main goal of teaching a foreign language at all stages of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan is to form a communicative competence in a foreign language for students to carry out activities in the everyday, scientific and professional spheres in the multicultural world. Requirements for the level of training of graduates of all levels of foreign language teaching in this document, competence are divided into the following groups: linguistic, sociolinguistic and pragmatic competence. “Linguistic competence implies the acquisition of knowledge about language material (phonetics, lexicon, grammar) and skills in the types of speech activity (listening, speaking, reading and writing). Sociolinguistic competence makes it possible to choose the desired linguistic form, method of expression, based on one speech situation, communicative goal and desire of the speaker. Pragmatic competence implies the ability to get out of difficult situations through repeated requests, apologies, etc., when misunderstandings arise in the foreign language being studied in a communicative situation.” U.Hashimov and I.Yakubov point out that the main linguistic material of speech activity includes phonetic, grammatical and lexical material.

Characteristics of the language material, the various features of speech activity that activates them, they are selected on the basis of special principles. Each language material has its own selection principles. J.Jalalov, on the other hand, recommends: “it is possible to say that skill is an automated part of speech activity and to recommend the concept of lexical, grammatical and pronunciation skills of types of speech activity. It is desirable that the speech activity itself be called a qualification.” In addition, it is emphasized that the foreign language material should be understood as the entire lexical, grammatical and pronunciation material of the studied language.

On the other hand, the language minimum refers to that part of the language material that is useful and selected for the learning process from the inside, and is called lexical, grammatical and pronunciation minimum. The following foreign language units are listed:

- vocabulary (central word; compound word);
- lexical unit (compound word; compound word; word-forming element; stable phrase; sentence; (taught without division into parts in the context of the development of oral speech);
- grammatical unit (morphology phenomenon; syntax phenomenon);
- pronunciation unit (sound – from phoneme to intonation of sentences);
- spelling unit (letter; letter combination; word; word formation; construction of the form, alternating and non-permanent forms of the word).

Researchers D.A.Gusev, O.V.Fleurov defined the linguistic component as a special knowledge of the language that a person possesses related to various aspects of the language, namely grammar, phonetics and vocabulary, as well as skills and abilities associated with them. They believe that if we are taught to communicate in a foreign language, it will not be enough to restrict language learners to a linguistic code on the contrary, it is also necessary to develop the ability to use language in specific situations of social contacts.

While teaching linguistic aspects, deductive and inductive methods are recommended, with the deductive method, the first topic (grammatical rules, new words) is explained and examples are given, new sentences and texts in the language being studied are built on the basis of these explanations. Unlike the deductive method, the inductive method allows students to

discover a new topic on their own, that is, they try to develop a rule by studying the rules, and then get acquainted with examples, not examples.

For example, after students finish reading the text, they will be asked How to find examples of the past simple tense in the text and how they were made, what they were used for, and then students themselves will create a rule based on discussions. In the development of grammatical competence on the basis of a learner centered approach, situational presentations, text and written tapes are used, training by the method of "control- training -control" (Teach test Teach) is highlighted by D. Riedel. When teaching grammatical competence using the "control-training-control" method, the teacher explains the subject using a series of tasks after checking how much students are aware or not aware of the subject.

Through this way, students will also be aware of information about their knowledge and will be able to take responsibility in the learning process. Because students create working conditions together, teach each other and share what they know with each other. As the ultimate goal of learning the grammatical competence of Pratima Dave Shastri, language learners should be able to learn and support the language accordingly, to use the same things in different tasks in different ways. Unlike formal or descriptive grammar, functional grammar is recommended to be taught by language learners with a communicative approach, in combination with other language skills, within a context, using the inductive method. In the development of phonetic competence, Penny Ur (Penny Ur) gave several recommendations:

- return of the teacher or sounds, words or sentences by analogy and imitation of a copy recorded in the tape;
- analysis of the speech of a language learner by writing it on tape, comparison of the speech of local users;
- be regularly aware of pronunciation rules and constructs;
- use of drill exercises: repetition of sounds, pronunciation of words and sentences;
- execution by learning dialogues;
- repetition of exercises in the choir;
- memorization and execution of sentences, fast words and rhymes (rhymes);
- the language learner records his voice on tape, listens, analyzes and corrects his mistakes.

J.Jalalov argues that training pronunciation is of particular importance, and cites three parts of pronunciation: auditory (acoustic), speaking (motor) and signifying (semantic). When choosing a pronunciation minimum, methodological criteria are presented, including:

- 1) the proportionality of the phonetic unit to the need for speech communication;
- 2) style suitable for choice;
- 3) normativity of pronunciation;
- 4) wide prevalence.

Unlike grammatical and lexical competence, during the formation of phonetic competence, active (pronounced) and passive (audible) pronunciation units are simultaneously mastered, while listening indicates that internal speech occurs, while pronouncing - external. In the methodology of teaching English, the teaching of lexical competence is shown as a means of mastering the types of speech activity.

Teaching vocabulary in the methodology of teaching English is a process consisting of two stages. The first is the stage of methodological preparation of the lexicon (selection),

distribution, classification, presentation, and this process is carried out by Methodists of this field. The second is the stage of the formation of lexical skills, in the process of which the teacher and the student directly operate in cooperation. In conclusion, it should be noted that in the development of competencies of a foreign language, a learner centered approach is significant. This is due to the fact that students are constantly aware of their knowledge and have the opportunity to take responsibility in the learning process. Alternatively, students create conditions for collaboration, teach each other and share with each other what they know.

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